

1 **Supporting information**

2 **Fig. S1** Decrease in relative water content (RWC) of leaf samples of tobacco and barley with time after
3 their detachment

4 **Fig. S2** Micrographs of leaf structure of fresh tobacco (A) and barley (B) leaves.

5 **Fig. S3** WI_{SWIR} images of representative desiccating tobacco and barley leaf samples. Numbers above
6 the samples indicate their RWC in %.

7 **Fig. S4** (A) Leaf area (in % of the area of fresh leaves) and (B) equivalent water thickness (EWT) during
8 desiccation of tobacco and barley leaf samples.

9 **Fig. S5** Imaging of chlorophyll fluorescence parameters of representative desiccating tobacco and
10 barley leaf samples. The maximum quantum yield of PSII photochemistry (F_V/F_M), the effective
11 quantum yield of PSII photochemistry in the light-adapted state ($\Phi_{PSII_{st}}$), the non-photochemical
12 quenching of chlorophyll fluorescence after 1 min of exposure to actinic light (NPQ_1), and the non-
13 photochemical quenching of Chl fluorescence at steady state (NPQ_{st}).

14 **Fig. S6** Dependencies of measured parameters on RWC (in interval 100-50%) in desiccating tobacco
15 leaves and segments. The parameters are ranked from most to least reliable according to their
16 coefficient of reliability (CR). All parameters are normalized to their mean value (\bar{y}).

17 **Fig. S7** Dependencies of measured parameters on RWC (in interval 100-50%) in desiccating barley
18 leaves and segments. The parameters are ranked from most to least reliable according to their
19 coefficient of reliability (CR). All parameters are normalized to their mean value (\bar{y}).

20 **Fig. S8** Leaf water potential measured by psychrometry (Ψ_{psy}) and by pressure chamber (Ψ_{press}) in
21 desiccating leaves of tobacco (A) and barley (B).

22 **Table S1** Parameters measured on desiccating leaf samples ranked according to their coefficient of
23 sensitivity (CS) within the RWC interval 100-50% in tobacco and barley.

24 **Table S2** Parameters measured on desiccating leaf samples ranked according to their coefficient of
25 inaccuracy (CI) within the RWC interval 100-50% in tobacco and barley.

26 **Table S3** Ranking of measured parameters according to their coefficient of reliability (CR), sensitivity
27 (CS) and inaccuracy (CI) in desiccating leaf samples of tobacco and barley within the RWC interval 100-
28 50%. The parameters have been divided into 5 groups (the first column) according to the type of leaf
29 characteristics they reflect.

30 **Table S4** Approximate time required for the measurement of the parameters used in the study and
31 the destructiveness/non-destructiveness of the measurement.

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34 **Fig. S1** Decrease in relative water content (RWC) of leaf samples of tobacco and barley with time
 35 after their detachment

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39 **Fig. S2** Micrographs of leaf structure of fresh tobacco (A) and barley (B) leaves.

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42 **Fig. S3** WISWIR images of representative desiccating tobacco and barley leaf samples. Numbers above
 43 the samples indicate their RWC in %.

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48 **Fig. S4** (A) Leaf area (in % of the area of fresh leaves) and (B) equivalent water thickness (EWT) during
 49 desiccation of tobacco and barley leaf samples.

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52 **Fig. S5** Imaging of chlorophyll fluorescence parameters of representative desiccating tobacco and
 53 barley leaf samples. The maximum quantum yield of PSII photochemistry (F_V/F_M), the effective
 54 quantum yield of PSII photochemistry in the light-adapted state ($\Phi_{PSII_{st}}$), the non-photochemical
 55 quenching of chlorophyll fluorescence after 1 min of exposure to actinic light (NPQ_1), and the non-
 56 photochemical quenching of Chl fluorescence at steady state (NPQ_{st}).

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 59 leaves and segments. The parameters are ranked from most to least reliable according to their
 60 coefficient of reliability (CR). All parameters are normalized to their mean value (\bar{y}).

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62 **Fig. S7** Dependencies of measured parameters on RWC (in interval 100-50%) in desiccating barley
 63 leaves and segments. The parameters are ranked from most to least reliable according to their
 64 coefficient of reliability (CR). All parameters are normalized to their mean value (\bar{y}).

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66 **Fig. S8** Leaf water potential measured by psychrometry (Ψ_{psy}) and by pressure chamber (Ψ_{press}) in
 67 desiccating leaves of tobacco (A) and barley (B).

68 **Table S1** Parameters measured on desiccating leaf samples ranked according to their coefficient of
 69 sensitivity (*CS*) within the RWC interval 100-50% in tobacco and barley.

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Ranking	Tobacco		Barley		
	parameter	CS	parameter	CS	
71					
72	1	NPQ ₁	4.1322	ψ_{psy}	4.151
73	2	ψ_{press}	4.0544	ψ_{press}	2.532
74	3	ψ_{psy}	2.5562	NPQ _{st}	1.3143
75	4	ΔR_D	1.9394	NPQ ₁	0.8084
76	5	$\Phi\text{PSII}_{\text{st}}$	1.7802	$\Phi\text{PSII}_{\text{st}}$	0.6856
77	6	ΔR_B	1.2813	WI _{SWIR}	0.5567
78	7	NPQ _{st}	0.8246	ΔR_B	0.4397
79	8	SPAD	0.6892	ΔR_D	0.3718
80	9	NDVI _B	0.4759	SPAD	0.1738
81	10	F _V /F _M	0.3777	NDVI _B	0.0733
	11	NDVI _D	0.1349	NDVI _D	0.0588
	12	WI _{SWIR}	0.0941	WI _B	0.0391
	13	WI _B	0.0039	WI _D	0.0293
	14	WI _D	0.0001	F _V /F _M	0.0247

82 **Table S2** Parameters measured on desiccating leaf samples ranked according to their coefficient of
 83 inaccuracy (*CI*) within the RWC interval 100-50% in tobacco and barley.

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Ranking by <i>CI</i>	Tobacco		Barley	
	parameter	CI	parameter	CI
1	WI _D	0.2223	WI _D	0.1842
2	WI _B	0.3338	WI _B	0.3845
3	NDVI _D	3.2451	F _V /F _M	0.5557
4	NDVI _B	4.4186	NDVI _B	3.7123
5	F _V /F _M	5.648	NDVI _D	4.2113
6	WI _{SWIR}	8.8267	SPAD	4.301
7	SPAD	9.3367	$\Phi\text{PSII}_{\text{st}}$	4.6556
8	ψ_{psy}	10.2149	WI _{SWIR}	8.8267
9	ΔR_B	14.1805	NPQ _{st}	13.7623
10	$\Phi\text{PSII}_{\text{st}}$	15.0133	ΔR_D	14.7797
11	NPQ _{st}	16.9332	ψ_{psy}	15.3932
12	ΔR_D	23.3475	ΔR_B	15.5571
13	ψ_{press}	33.6285	NPQ ₁	15.6153
14	NPQ ₁	34.3444	ψ_{press}	46.628

85 **Table S3** Ranking of measured parameters according to their coefficient of reliability (*CR*), sensitivity
 86 (*CS*) and inaccuracy (*CI*) in desiccating leaf samples of tobacco and barley within the RWC interval 100-
 87 50%. The parameters have been divided into 5 groups (the first column) according to the type of leaf
 88 characteristics they reflect.

	parameter	Tobacco			Barley		
		<i>CR</i>	<i>CS</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>CS</i>	<i>CI</i>
Leaf water potential	ψ_{psy}	1	3	8	1	1	11
	ψ_{press}	2	2	13	10	2	14
	Σ	3	5	21	11	3	25
Water indices	WI_B	12	13	2	2	12	2
	WI_D	14	14	1	4	13	1
	WI_{SWIR}	13	12	6	5	6	8
	Σ	39	39	9	11	31	11
Leaf structure	ΔR_B	6	6	9	11	7	12
	ΔR_D	7	4	12	12	8	10
	Σ	13	10	21	23	15	22
Chlorophyll content	$NDVI_B$	5	9	4	13	10	4
	$NDVI_D$	11	11	3	14	11	5
	SPAD	8	8	7	10	9	6
	Σ	24	28	14	37	30	15
Chlorophyll fluorescence (photochemistry)	F_V/F_M	9	10	5	9	14	3
	$\Phi_{\text{PSII}_{\text{st}}}$	4	5	10	3	5	7
	NPQ_1	3	1	14	8	4	13
	NPQ_{st}	10	7	11	6	3	9
	Σ	26	23	40	26	26	32

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91 **Table S4** Approximate time required for the measurement of the parameters used in the study and
 92 the destructiveness/non-destructiveness of the measurement. The parameters that were used for the
 93 comparison according to their coefficients of reliability (*CR*), sensitivity (*CS*) and inaccuracy (*CI*) are
 94 written in bold.

Method	Instrument	Parameter(s)	Time requirement	Destructive
Spectral reflectance (diffusive)	spectroradiometer with integrating sphere	$R_B, R_D,$	15 min	yes
		$\Delta R_B, \Delta R_D,$		
		$WI_B, WI_D,$		
		$NDVI_B, NDVI_D$		
Spectral reflectance (directional)	SWIR camera	WI_{SWIR}	minutes	no
	PolyPen	NDVI	seconds	
Transmittance	chlorophyllmeter SPAD-502	SPAD	seconds	no
Chlorophyll fluorescence	fluorescence imaging system	F_v/F_M	seconds	no
		NPQ_1	1 min	no
		$\Phi PSII_{st}, NPQ_{st}$	10 min	no
Psychrometry	psychrometric chamber	Ψ_{psy}	hours	yes
Pressure chamber	pressure chamber	Ψ_{press}	minutes	yes

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